

ETIOLOGY OF SOCIAL SECURITY WITHIN THE SPECTRUM OF CONTEMPORARY CRISIS PHENOMENA

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Abstract

The inevitability of the emergence of security, as an outcome of the processes of operationalization and personification of individual social needs for the protection of personal and societal values, has resulted in the formation of social security systems. Two key characteristics of security systems determine their nature: the influence of individual activity and the interconnectedness of their functioning (Adomeit, 1982). An individual cannot fully satisfy personal needs – especially security needs – independently, because the spectrum of threats to human beings is so broad that many remain unrecognized until they manifest at the societal level. At the same time, individuals inevitably enter relationships with others through processes of production, distribution, and consumption, which exposes them to risks generated within society, either individually or collectively. Social processes may arise from the activities of individuals or society as a whole, but they may also result from the passivity of these same actors.

Security, as a social phenomenon and process, emerged as a response to the problem of satisfying human needs for a safe environment for living and working. The effects and directions of social processes generate both phenomena of creation (progress) and phenomena of destruction (endangerment). The constant fluctuation of social relations leads to the emergence of both. Phenomena characterized by the endangerment of protected societal values have been recognized as crises. Security, as a phenomenon, has therefore been tasked with identifying ways to define the social space for prevention and response in various crisis situations. According to a number of authors, the terms *social security* and *security of society* should be regarded as synonymous.

This paper analyzes the conditions for the emergence and development of security as an essential human need in relation to the environment. Variations of the environment can

be examined separately in order to elaborate the precise influence of different factors on the protected values of society. The operationalization of the research subject is based on the author's previous studies in the fields of security and crises and is directed toward demonstrating a causal relationship between security and crises. The central research question is whether a cause-and-effect relationship exists between social security and crises as a general phenomenon.

The paper was created on the basis of research within the project "Contemporary Crises and the Safety of Society." The results of the research were partially published in the paper "The Safety of Society Based on the Concept of Crisis" (Collection of Papers FBN Banja Luka, ISBN 978-99976-805-7-0).

Keywords: Crisis, Security, Society

1. CONCEPT AND METHOD

The abstraction and concretization of the concept of crisis continue to generate the absence of a precise definition, as well as a clear explanation of its emergence and development. The implications for security also remain undefined and at the level of general understanding and a set of assumptions. Research into the causal relationship between social security and crises opens space for the analysis of segments for which developmental assumptions exist, as well as segments that arise from events with specific implications. The interpretation of events that disrupt social security within certain frameworks and segments lacks methodological grounding in terms of information quality and sampling. Nevertheless, such events provide important guidelines for shaping the conceptual framework of research into the causal relationship between social security and crises.

The theoretical research model allows the researcher to formulate hypotheses with a higher degree of freedom, with the aim of modeling scenarios through which certain conclusions may be reached. Given the fact that crises represent a concept without a long research tradition, it is necessary to establish logical relations of influence on social security within the broadest possible hypothetical spectrum, primarily in order to identify future directions of action. This observation is particularly important for distinguishing crises from other concepts of social security disruption that produce certain consequences, but not at the level of a crisis.

Under conditions of a high degree of uncertainty, the key challenge for the researcher lies in selecting appropriate research methods. Given the vagueness and insufficient development of theoretical postulates related to crises, the study applies content analysis of theoretical works by authors who have examined societal security problems from various perspectives, as well as authors who have analyzed their implications in practical contexts. In addition, scenario modeling is used to provide potential insights into the implications of crises for social security, without necessarily offering definitive answers, as such models primarily open the next level of research questions.

The paper does not employ specific crisis case studies to substantiate particular conditions, precisely in order to avoid directing the research toward conclusions driven by a single crisis. The fundamental postulate is to preserve the breadth of crisis impacts on social security and to use the uncertainty of their implications as a basic characteristic of crises.

2. SOCIAL PRECONDITIONS OF SECURITY

In the new century, a universalist idea has developed that promotes the establishment of a new, more just international order, in which ethics would prevail over force and oppression, and the power of weapons would be replaced by the power of public opinion. Today, the idea of universality serves as a platform for the theory of globalism. However, globalism has not produced solutions that have enhanced societal security. On the contrary, it has led to even deeper divisions among individual societies organized as states. At the same time, the idea of a single world society has been losing momentum and developmental capacity. In parallel with this process, specific mechanisms have emerged, based on international law and international relations, aimed at creating a world society governed from a single center.

2.1. Danger as a Precondition for the Emergence of Security

What is dangerous and how to act in the presence of danger are questions that humans have sought to answer since their very origin. Human history is filled with events that have produced dramatic and destructive effects, resulting in severe negative consequences. Events and situations that threatened human survival appeared in various forms, with different intensities and characteristics. In such circumstances, throughout evolutionary and socio-cultural development, humans have attempted in various ways to suppress dangers within their environment that limited or obstructed the fulfillment of their needs. Different events acted in different ways, but one element remained common: humans experienced suffering and were prevented from satisfying their needs. The adversities affecting humans were unpredictable, multidimensional, and unrestricted in time and space, while their effects were often devastating.

Various efforts to prevent, or at least reduce, events with negative effects resulted in different measures undertaken to achieve a certain level of protection. Although scientific achievements have reached a very high level of development, humans continue to face the same or similar dangers, whose effects have been multiplied due to increased hazard capacities driven by technological development and higher population density per spatial unit. These facts imply the human need to exist in an environment free from danger, or in which dangers are so limited that they do not restrict the fulfillment of basic needs. An environment without the presence of danger is referred to as a secure environment (Almond, 1973).

In addition to the substantive definition of danger, it is necessary to consider elements related to the capacity for protection once danger materializes. The human need for protection, and the ability or inability to provide a certain level of protection, indicate the state of security at a given moment. The relationship between these two states is characterized by a degree of imbalance that reflects the level of security. Specifically, when needs are high and capabilities are low, security is low; conversely, when needs are low and capabilities are high, security reaches a satisfactory level (Almond et al., 1973).

Finally, the fundamental characteristic of danger – at the same time the central focus of human interest in the struggle for a secure environment – lies in its consequences. Consequences represent the effects that danger produces on humans and their values. For individuals and society, negative consequences are of primary concern. Human reasoning and action are therefore directed toward identifying measures that enable effective intervention against danger in order to mitigate or reduce its consequences. Positive consequences are secondary in nature but carry equal importance, as they possess developmental potential.

2.2. Endangerment as a Social Phenomenon

Various forms of danger, with a portfolio of consequences, alongside other factors influencing human existence, have directed individuals toward association and collective action. People quickly recognized the advantages of grouping and cooperation in terms of achieving more effective protection. Thus, danger and endangerment ceased to be an individual matter and became the concern of a group or society. This raises the question of why endangerment became relevant to society as a whole. Since endangerment represents a set of interconnected phenomena, processes, interactions, and sources of origin, it can be concluded that it affects all social flows and processes, as well as all social groups. Accordingly, endangerment constitutes a social phenomenon that, through a specific event or sustained pattern of behavior in social life, produces negative consequences (Bajagić, 2007).

A central place in the process of societal endangerment is occupied by the values that society seeks to protect and preserve. Societal values represent the very essence of the human struggle for a secure environment and, in the context of social life, may refer to moral and social achievements, culture, material goods, and similar elements.

The social character of endangerment is reflected in the fact that society is threatened by various dangers, such as other social groups, natural hazards, and its own technical and technological development. The diversity of threats implies a diversity of protective measures that must be undertaken. An individual lacks the capacity to implement large-scale measures, whereas society possesses such capabilities. Social development has therefore generated the need for a systemic approach to developing measures for the protection of societal values, as well as mechanisms organized into various specialized fields (Beck, 1992).

An important aspect in defining societal endangerment is the cause of endangerment. Endangerment arises when necessary and sufficient conditions converge to produce danger – that is, when sources of danger emerge (Savić et al, 2009). From this, it can be concluded that not all processes and events in society and its environment constitute danger or possess a primary endangering character. This characteristic indicates that the diversity of causes determines the nature of endangerment, which may manifest as a natural, social, or psychological phenomenon (Blummer, Gurewicz, 1995). Endangerment caused by natural phenomena refers to natural disasters and other accidents, while endangerment caused by social phenomena includes various types of wars, terrorist acts, and similar events. The psychological component of endangerment lies in the fact that such phenomena often manifest as conscious activities of individuals or social groups aimed at achieving a specific goal. In certain circumstances, awareness of a particular goal itself may constitute a cause of endangerment.

A specific position in the interpretation of endangerment as a social phenomenon is held by the issue of the object of endangerment. The object of endangerment is closely linked to societal values. The content of societal values as objects of endangerment is determined by the goals and tasks of society. Depending on these goals, the definition of protected objects includes institutional forms of society, such as the political system, territory, human lives, and similar elements. In this way, manifestations of societal endangerment are simultaneously concretized, since there is no endangerment without a societal value as its object (Bovens, 't Hart, 1996).

The development of social relations has also implied the development of perspectives on the possibilities of societal endangerment. Such considerations led to the conclusion that it is not sufficient to protect only the fundamental societal value – human

life. A need emerged to protect material assets, social institutions, the environment, and other values.

Contemporary society, owing to a high level of technological advancement, has achieved a high level of development in measures and systems for protecting societal values from endangerment. Threatening phenomena are no longer unknown; rather, their content is known to a certain extent. In most cases, uncertainty remains regarding the timing and intensity of their realization. The evolution of social relations has introduced new challenges with varying degrees of uncertainty.

2.3. The Emergence and Development of Security as a Social Phenomenon

The concepts of endangerment and security are closely related and are commonly used to define one another. The relationship between these two concepts places them in an opposing position: when speaking of a state of security, a state of endangerment stands in contrast. From this perspective, both concepts are value-neutral (Larousse, 1999). This neutrality is reflected in the fact that phenomena threatening society – whether of natural or social origin – result from the behavior of individuals, groups, or states, regardless of whether such behavior or phenomena are positive or negative, or whether they have a developmental or destructive character (Byrne & Baden, 1995).

Security represents a fundamental human need, a universal goal, and a guarantee of a free life without fear and suffering. Contemporary interpretations by various authors indicate that the most common understanding of security assumes that the term refers to a specific state, activity, organization, function, system, or a combination of these (Charles & 't Hart, 2008). Accordingly, security may be understood as a state of absence of danger to the fundamental values and interests of individuals and society – a state that ensures the protection of all members of a social community through planned, rational, and conscious human activity. As a system, security is consciously oriented toward a specific goal, organized, and based on an appropriate theoretical orientation, doctrinal framework, and legal foundation. Within the security system, numerous interwoven and dynamic, yet structured connections and functional relationships exist, implying the possibility of modeling and management.

Security as a phenomenon can be viewed through two approaches: negativist and positivist. The negativist approach defines security as the absence of endangerment. However, if such a stance is adopted, the question arises as to what constitutes endangerment. If endangerment implies the negative potential of phenomena in relation to societal values, and security is defined as the absence of such endangerment, then this approach assumes the absence of negative potential in threatening phenomena –that is, the nonexistence of endangerment. This approach requires the identification and enumeration of all forms and carriers of threats to societal values, which vary from case to case (Dragišić, 2007). Ultimately, this approach does not provide a comprehensive answer to the question of what security is and what its scope entails.

The positivist approach implies a substantive understanding of security. It defines what security is by determining its content. Given that the existence of security presupposes a state without danger, security can be considered a societal value – political, moral, economic, cultural, and others. It represents a value because it does not merely imply the absence of danger, but also the presence of morality, justice, and culture as phenomena and processes (Fiamengo, 1974).

The value of security, particularly in contemporary society, may constitute a value in itself, as it enables the functioning of other societal functions. As a social phenomenon, security emerges as a complex and pervasive factor that influences all segments of society.

Researchers approach the consideration and study of security from different perspectives. Various approaches (realist, neorealist, globalist, and others) and levels (national, human, social, global) are present in the observation of the concept of security. Additional ambiguity in definition arises from the problem of determining who should ensure security, how, and by what means for individuals and social groups. Despite differing views and approaches, there is consensus that, under contemporary conditions, security must be regarded as a fundamental value and a regularity in the development of humans, society, the state, and humanity, encompassing both the security of social structures and the security of natural living conditions. Contemporary debates therefore address security as an essential need, value, and interest of both individuals and society.

2.4. The Contemporary Security Context

For a long time, the concept of security was constructed primarily in relation to military projections of threats, which remains a significant influential factor even today. However, the progress and development of technical and technological capabilities in the contemporary world have not only enhanced military threats but have also increased non-military security threats. As a result, security no longer represents merely an understanding of the nature of threats, but also an understanding of the ways in which security threats are shaped and manifested. This approach emerged from the need to respond to the growing number of threats within the security domain. Owing to major political and economic changes at the end of the twentieth century and the increasing prevalence of non-military security threats, the focus of security shifted from a state-centric perspective toward the individual and society (Hajmans, 2006).

A holistic approach to the understanding and conceptualization of security has thus emerged. This approach refers to a condition of protection of the vital interests of individuals, society, and the state from internal and external threats and risks of various natures and characteristics, at both global and local levels.

The diversity of social, political, and economic factors within the new social context has overshadowed the primarily social character of security, due to the inevitable emergence of its technical dimension. This fact points to a multidimensional perception of security, arising from the need to interpret security not merely as a prerequisite for the fulfillment of basic life functions and the survival and activity of individuals or groups.

New approaches to observing security phenomena indicate the existence of a need for security-oriented behavior, within which security attitudes of individuals and groups are developed and maintained, with the aim of fostering awareness of their necessity. The long-standing reference object of security – the state – has gradually shifted from the central framework of the security concept, with the individual assuming its place. This change in the consideration of the reference object of security has led to a transformation in the meaning of many security-related concepts. Among them is the notion of *security culture*, which has gained renewed significance in contemporary security discourse by emphasizing behavior in the security context. Although this concept had earlier theoretical foundations, it has acquired its full meaning through the elevation of the individual to the central position within security thinking (Nye, 2003).

The continuous and irreversible process of security transformation has been reflected in changes in the understanding of the security concept itself. Consequently, the

state is no longer the primary subject of interest in security studies. Its central position has been assumed by transnational and international organizations, nations, national minorities, various professional and marginalized groups, and, most importantly, individuals as the most numerous actors within the security framework (Nye, 2003).

As the number of reference objects of security increases, interest in security culture also grows. At the same time, the expansion of reference objects renders the meaning of security culture increasingly complex. The central question of security culture is no longer how to educate and socialize an entire nation in the field of security, but rather how to address each individual separately (’t Hart et al, 1993). Accordingly, security-related education and socialization must begin “from the base,” where individuals are the primary focus, while simultaneously being addressed “from the top,” where society at the national, regional, and international levels constitutes the target.

3. THE PHENOMENON OF CRISIS AND SECURITY

Does the disruption of a person’s security environment generate demands on the individual or social actor to engage extraordinary capacities in order to protect personal aspirations and needs? The answer is certainly affirmative. The fulfillment of basic human needs constitutes the fundamental condition of human existence. When the ability to realize these needs at a fundamental level is disrupted, a state emerges that deviates from what is considered “normal.” The newly created condition, in which individuals and society must invest additional time and resources and alter the circumstances in which they function in order to return to a regular and desired state, constitutes a crisis.

The essence of a crisis lies in the disruption of normal processes within a given social system. New conditions emerge in various forms and manifestations. The phenomenon of crisis, in the context of human security, has become the subject of research by a large number of scholars. Researchers examining different types of crises have identified a wide range of factors that may cause disruptions in the fulfillment of human needs or in the functioning of society. In crisis-related analyses, disruption is used in its broadest sense to indicate that environmental conditions have changed in such a way that individuals or society no longer function under desired circumstances.

3.1. The Concept of Contemporary Crises

Crises represent transitional phases during which normal modes of functioning no longer apply. A crisis is defined as “a serious threat to the basic structures or fundamental values and norms of a social system which, under conditions of time pressure and highly uncertain circumstances, requires the making of critical decisions” (Rosenthal et al., 1989). A significant advantage of this definition lies in its applicability to all types of disruptions, including environmental threats, failures of information technology infrastructure, economic crises, intra-state conflicts, prison riots, regional wars, and natural disasters. Crises may also be defined as unplanned and undesired processes of limited duration, which can be influenced to some extent and may end in different ways (Karovic & Komazec, 2009).

In efforts to reconcile different perspectives, the term “crisis” is often used as a “catch-all concept,” encompassing all types of negative events. In an even broader sense, the term is applied to situations that are undesired, unexpected, unpredictable, and almost unimaginable, generating uncertainty and insecurity (Rosenthal et al., 1989). Such an understanding of crisis contains three key components: threat, uncertainty, and urgency. Crises arise when essential values or systems that support existential needs come under the

influence of threatening forces. When deeply rooted and widely shared values – such as safety and security, social welfare, health, and justice – become uncertain or even meaningless under the negative impact of an impending disaster, it is evident that profound negative effects occur at both individual and community levels. The dependence of a secure life on these values is directly proportional to the depth of the crisis, and vice versa.

The perception of threats in a crisis is inevitably accompanied by a high degree of uncertainty (Flin, 1996). The conceptualization of crisis as a period of discontinuity, marking a breaking point in a linear process that normally unfolds according to established patterns, is rooted in classical approaches within sociology and political science. Within this type of definition, crisis is viewed as a disruption of normality. From the perspective of contemporary social science research, such an approach is problematic, as it resembles structural-functional analysis. Nevertheless, this type of definition helps overcome shortcomings associated with the “decision-making” character of crises. The essence of action in a crisis lies in decision-making aimed at stabilizing the situation and initiating the process of returning to a desired state.

3.2. The Conditionality of Crises by Social Conflicts and Interests

Crises result from multiple and multidimensional causes that collectively generate threats with destructive potential. This understanding challenges conventional practice, as it opposes the traditional logic of “triggers and causes” assumed to lie behind events. It is commonly believed that a specific set of factors causes a crisis, after which distinctions are made between internal and external causes. However, it is more accurate to speak of increasingly intensive processes that undermine the capacity of social systems to cope with disturbances. The core issue is that a crisis may originate from virtually any source, but its fundamental cause lies in the system’s inability to manage disruptions. This raises a logical question: are modern systems becoming more vulnerable to disturbances? The answer is twofold.

One perspective indicates improved societal resilience through the development of modern technologies, which enhance society’s capacity to address routine failures. The other perspective points to the deterioration of resilience in social systems, manifested through the emergence of disturbances that produce negative effects affecting all actors.

The very quality of complex systems that drives progress lies at the heart of most, if not all, technological crises. As socio-technical systems become more complex and increasingly interconnected with their subsystems, their sensitivity to disturbances grows exponentially. The risk of interaction multiplication – both horizontal and vertical – emerges abruptly due to the tight interconnection of systems with other systems.

Globalization occupies a distinct position in social life from the perspective of societal vulnerability to disturbances. As a process connecting global markets and financial systems, globalization creates unified systems of global culture and security. Its processes and principles erase boundaries and increase sensitivity to disturbances as a result of accelerated technological expansion, rapid communication, and the development of global awareness, which often leads to the neglect of real local problems.

According to Labović, a particular aspect of the crisis paradigm with a wide range of implications is systemically corrupt politics, which generates a systemic crisis and continuously and cyclically produces smaller or larger security, political, institutional, constitutional, and economic crises, especially in underdeveloped countries. In economically developed countries, a systemically corrupt foreign policy evolves, which permanently generates economic, political, ecological, and military crises worldwide in order to achieve

the goals of the neoliberal doctrine through extraterritorial imperialist neocolonialism (Labović, 2024).

All too often, the phrase “systemic corruption” leads to political and normative statements that usually express its categorical rejection and assign blame to the actors involved. Yet, despite decades of efforts to combat systemic corruption, the global map of corruption remains red to dark red in many countries. Such an approach remains tied to the everyday theoretical understanding of the phenomenon, but it nevertheless introduces four important indicators and distinctions: (1) regularity in the occurrence of corruption. “The relevant type of corruption (1) persists and continues over time, (2) involves the participation, whether conscious or not, of multiple actors, and (3) takes the form of a recognizable institutional practice, (4) thereby implying a certain degree of coordination among the participants” (Ceva & Radoilska, 2018). In other words, systemic corruption does not occur only regularly, but also simultaneously or in an interconnected manner across different spheres of society, involving many members of a given society.

Without the intention of providing a more detailed analysis of this phenomenon, it is important to draw attention to it, as can be inferred from Labović’s works, since it will significantly affect the security dimension of social life at both the national and global levels in the future.

The nonlinear dynamics and complexity of social activities complicate the detection of crises. The growing complexity of contemporary systems also complicates their comprehension, making it more difficult to identify the multitude of factors and activities occurring within them. Increasing system fragility becomes progressively harder to recognize, while ineffective attempts to manage minor problems persist. In this way, systems foster latent crises (Rijpma, 1997). The roots of a crisis may be geographically distant, yet the crisis can rapidly expand through global networks, spreading from one system to another, increasing its destructive potential while simultaneously increasing opportunities for progress.

3.3. The Impact of Modern Crisis Trends on Security

Modern crises differ substantially from events traditionally studied under the concept of crises. Contemporary crises exhibit endemic characteristics, indicating that they are a logical correlate of increasingly complex systems that, for technological, financial, social, or political reasons, are unable to meet security requirements. By their nature, modern crises are complex: they consist of new combinations of familiar crises that seemingly point toward solutions which, in practice, often become sources of further escalation. Moreover, modern crises tend toward self-perpetuation; the process turns into a vicious circle sustained by insecurity and uncertainty regarding causes and causal chains. There is no simple return to normality, as future crises re-emerge in altered forms. A modern crisis is also a result of the way individuals and societies perceive values and threats. At the same time, it represents a logical consequence of dominant trends that have shaped, and continue to shape, contemporary society.

Contemporary theory identifies several phenomena that more precisely define the impact of crises on societal security: transnationalization, the media society, the erosion of state authority, and technological development as universal principles. The evolution of conditions under which modern societies build their capacities has also led to the emergence of additional influential factors, including changes in the paradigm of international law and the increased riskiness of the global environment.

Transnationalization

Until the final decades of the twentieth century, security was almost exclusively linked to the state. National frameworks represented the central arena for the protection of national interests. However, negative events caused by both human and natural factors revealed the permeability of such an approach and redirected security perspectives toward regional and global levels. The effects of negative events were not confined within national borders but extended far beyond them (e.g., Chernobyl, Fukushima, pandemics, droughts). Crises do not recognize national boundaries, nor do they stop at them. Increasingly, crises are defined within regional and transnational frameworks (Rene, 1987).

The global scope of disasters has become more pronounced: two world wars, new conflicts whose escalation may lead to global confrontations, worldwide economic repression, nuclear accidents, and current environmental trends all require a global perspective. Although sources of problems may remain local or national, the immediate or long-term consequences of disasters and crises spread across countries and continents. The majority of catastrophes and crises in recent decades clearly demonstrate the importance of this transnational dimension (McCormick, 2005).

The Media Society

A crisis entails the collapse of the symbolic framework that legitimized the order within which people previously achieved a sense of security. The elements of normal, secure life disappear, giving rise to a chaotic condition of what remains. Crises generate multiple levels of uncertainty, from the individual to the collective. At the personal level, affected individuals face undeniable cognitive information that circumstances are deteriorating ('t Hart et al., 1993). At the societal level, this cognitive conflict is reflected in the activities of numerous groups and organizations that adopt differing interpretations of the situation, offering competing claims regarding causes, responses, and future developments. These problems are also characteristic of the international level.

To a large extent, cognitive uncertainty may be reduced or intensified depending on the actions undertaken by those in power. Political authorities build their credibility on the outcomes of their actions in crisis situations. Proposed solutions to crises, which do not necessarily coincide with expert recommendations, must nevertheless reach those affected by disasters (Nye, 2000).

The media tend to intensively cover two categories of events. First, they focus on ominous perspectives and the real-time unfolding of mega-disasters involving large numbers of potential or actual victims and extensive physical damage, driven by the appeal of timely and provocative information that attracts public attention. Second, the media display particular interest in subjective crisis phenomena characterized by panic, collective stress, and irrational behavior, which may weaken the normative structure of society.

A specific aspect of media influence is represented by social networks. Although the ambivalent nature of media may raise questions about the formal classification of social networks as media, they function in essence as powerful media channels. From the perspective of information dissemination, their capacity is exceptional. In addition to their utility, they may also constitute a significant negative factor by contributing to the spread of misinformation, panic, and similar effects.

Technological Development

The rapid and accelerating development of information and communication technologies, satellite communications, artificial intelligence, and the internet has dramatically altered human perceptions of temporal and spatial constraints. This technological development affects both the causes and characteristics of crises. Technology has become so complex that users often do not understand how it functions, complicating the detection and correction of operational failures. Successful design of technological systems requires close coupling of components, which increases the likelihood of cascading failures (Nye, 2003). The development of inherently high-risk technologies also expands the potential scope of crises. Growing dependence on computer systems renders social and economic systems increasingly vulnerable, particularly to threats from hackers and cyberterrorists.

A new dimension of high-risk technologies draws attention to medical technologies and genetic manipulation. The consequences of such developments may only become apparent after several generations, yet their impact could be irreversible. This trend is further exacerbated by the growing gap between megascience and the knowledge or understanding of political decision-makers.

Technological superiority confers strategic advantage (Stojanović, 2009). The increasing importance and application of artificial intelligence open unprecedented possibilities for generating crises and influencing fundamental perceptions of reality among individuals, companies, and social groups. Robotization and attempts to assign human capabilities to machines introduce new dimensions of future crises.

Erosion of State Authority

In countries characterized by neoliberal systems, the role of the state has diminished over recent decades. Traditional prerogatives of public authorities in times of crisis have given way to less clear and less authoritative definitions of the tasks that public institutions should perform in preventing, preparing for, and managing crises. This political and administrative trend has significant implications for the causes, characteristics, and consequences of crises.

The declining role of public authorities is further compounded by austerity policies and restrictive behavior during crises. As a result of declining performance, significant budget overruns, and reduced public legitimacy, new governments in Western countries have adopted New Public Management as a guiding principle (Blumer, 1995). Since the benefits of crisis management activities are far more difficult to quantify than their costs, such activities tend to be underestimated, potentially leading to reduced funding for prevention and response capacities (Kešetović & Keković, 2008).

Changes in the Paradigm of International Law

International law increasingly functions as a mechanism enabling major powers to act globally without prior authorization for planned actions. Unilateral initiatives, accompanied by tacit consent or non-intervention, allow international actors to pursue their objectives without regard for established norms of international law. Under such conditions, the configuration of international relations changes subtly at the global level. The consequences of such actions are diverse and long-term, but in all cases they become a platform for the emergence of future crises. This mode of action generates insecurity among states, as uncertainty prevails regarding future developments. The areas affected are

numerous: social issues, energy, cyber security, food and water security, pandemics, and others.

Riskiness of the Global Environment

Contemporary societies, operationalized through state systems, exist within an insecure, dynamic, and rapidly changing environment. Formerly dominant local influences have diminished, while global influences have become decisive. This reality directs attention to the growing number of risks that undermine the security and safety of modern societies. Even minimal disturbances in one part of the world can have smaller or larger repercussions on communities elsewhere. As a result, the list of risks affecting societies continues to expand. Societal resilience to negative influences decreases, while vulnerability increases. The future is likely to bring even more risks that will affect the security of social communities.

3.4. Risk Society and Contemporary Crises

The past two centuries have been marked by intense progress and development in technological, economic, and demographic terms. Such progress has led many theorists and practitioners to question whether it is entirely positive, what its effects are, and whether it is sustainable. This skepticism is grounded in the observation that, alongside progress, dangers have increased and evolved, threatening the destruction of both humanity and the planet. The world has become sharply divided into subject (human beings) and object (nature, society, technology). Philosophical postulates emphasizing the unity of humans and nature have been neglected and have lost their relevance. Humanity has pursued complete domination and ruthless exploitation of nature, the environment, and other human beings, with aspirations extending even toward the universe.

Science itself has partly served as an instrument of rational instrumentalization. A particularly significant contribution has been made by the ideology of excessive consumption, which has reinforced indifference toward both nature and other people. Consequently, the only certainty is that the future is “more uncertain than ever before” (Beck, 1992).

This pattern of societal development reveals increasing vulnerability. The culmination of progress is not reflected solely in technological advancement – which drives many other processes – but also in consciousness and culture, as well as in economics and security. Certain advanced, neoliberal-oriented societies have contributed to the creation of a distinct idea of unifying the world into a global village through globalization. Globalization, as a process, is itself a product of technological progress. Grounded in capitalist economics, global awareness, a global social system, and a military order, globalization seeks to erase national characteristics and subordinate them to global interests (Stojanović, 2009).

On these foundations, Ulrich Beck introduced the concept of the “risk society,” drawing attention to the consequences of progress and technological development, which generate cumulative dangers and risks whose scope cannot be predicted.

Risk society theory has opened conceptual space for understanding risk and has brought its social dimension into focus. It is evident that dangers and their consequences do not affect all members of society equally. Even in the relationship between individuals and authorities, disasters that clearly produce negative effects for citizens may represent merely an administrative disturbance for decision-makers until institutional consensus is reached regarding their nature. Although decision-making depends on numerous factors, the primary

object of the security system – the individual – inevitably bears the consequences of disasters.

This situation raises a fundamental question regarding the path out of the “age of uncertainty”: whether it lies in the continuation of Enlightenment-based rationalist notions of progress, or in the construction of a society founded on a different paradigm – one that acknowledges the need for progress and improved quality of life while also recognizing the existence of limits within which such progress must occur.

4. CONCLUSION

The altered global security configuration following the disappearance of bipolar confrontation has failed to deliver the expected results, namely an increase in security and the creation of unhindered conditions for progress. On the contrary, ideas of social justice, a unified market, and a shared culture have remained positive concepts with tangible effects primarily in wealthy countries, while for poorer countries the range of problems has expanded. The gap between rich and poor has widened, population growth – especially in poorer regions – has intensified, the economies of many states have weakened, and rapid technological development, particularly in the fields of nuclear energy and information technologies, has increased the number of threats. In addition, shortages of food and energy resources, a rise in terrorist acts, and an increased frequency of natural and other disasters further exacerbate insecurity.

These problems are no longer merely local or confined to national states. The spatial and temporal dimensions of contemporary threats have become negligible, as none of these dangers depends on physical state borders; they threaten both rich and poor societies alike. The decisive difference lies solely in the existence of capacities for protection or for preventing negative effects. The consequences for people, material assets, and the environment are long-term in nature, affect a large number of actors, generate fear and panic, and disrupt the normal functioning of society.

These conditions indicate that contemporary society exists in a particular state of uncertainty and instability, commonly referred to as crisis. However, the scale of a crisis – and even the recognition of its existence – depend on those in power, specifically on their perception of an immediate threat to the fundamental values of society that requires an urgent response under conditions of uncertainty and insecurity, and often on political interests that determine whether an event is framed as a crisis.

Crisis events thus represent a serious challenge for governing authorities and a profound security problem for individuals and society. Citizens justifiably expect society to protect them and provide a secure environment in which they can fulfill their needs. Yet the very conditions that enable prosperity and progress simultaneously act as the main drivers of the causes of crises. As a result of the growing number of dangerous events, both individuals and societies as a whole become increasingly sensitive even to disturbances with lower threatening capacity.

The vicious circle in which progress and development act as drivers of crises, and in which crises may in turn generate progress while progress generates new crises, is a defining characteristic of contemporary society. Human security and the security of the surrounding environment remain uncertain. Contemporary aspirations toward universal security, largely shaped through globalization, reveal outcomes manifested in domination and, in particular, the monopolized exploitation of global natural resources by megacorporations (Kovač, 2009).

Mechanisms of global domination by powerful states are realized through the imposition of dependent modernization and neocolonialism, the reduction of state territorial sovereignty, cultural imperialism, the provocation of internal conflicts, and the use of military force to achieve political interests. For states seeking to preserve their national identity while existing within a just international community, the current trajectory of globalization represents an expanded range of challenges to national values.

The existing global constellation is evidently in crisis, and future developments will be shaped by the aspirations and power of major states (Kovač, 2009). The security dimension of the contemporary world has become increasingly influenced by modern crises. The spectrum of crisis impacts on societies in the contemporary world is multidimensional, thereby increasing societal vulnerability and exposing the weakest links within social systems.

Based on the presented analysis, it can be concluded that a causal relationship exists between social security and crises. An insecure and uncertain security context creates preconditions for the emergence of crises. Conversely, all types of events and phenomena with the capacity to generate crises constitute sources of security disruption. Future research should focus on further specifying causal relationships between social security and crises, with the aim of empirically demonstrating the influence of particular conditions and phenomena.

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